

Synthesis, Properties and Characterisation of Diphenylantimony(III) *O,O'*-Alkylene (and Diphenyl) Dithiophosphates

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Diphenylantimony(III) chloride reacts with sodium/ammonium salts of *O,O'*-alkylene and diphenyldithiophosphoric acids in equimolar amounts in refluxing benzene to yield

$\text{Ph}_2\text{SbS}_2\text{POGO}$ (where, $G = -\text{CMe}_2\text{CMe}_2-$, $-\text{CH}_2\text{CMe}_2\text{CH}_2-$, $-\text{CH}_2\text{C}(\text{Et})_2\text{CH}_2-$, and $-\text{CMe}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CHMe}-$) and $\text{Ph}_2\text{SbS}_2\text{P}(\text{OPh})_2$. The complexes are viscous liquids or semi-solids, soluble in common organic solvents and monomeric in nature. These have been characterised on the basis of elemental analyses, molecular weight determinations, ir and nmr (^1H , ^{13}C and ^{31}P) spectral data which reveal bidentate behaviour of dithiophosphate moieties.

O,O'-Dialkyl dithiophosphoric acids constitute an important series of ligands which show an interesting versatility in their bonding modes (e.g. uni- as well as bi-dentate chelating/bridging) towards different metals¹⁻⁵. These also find wide applications as oil additives and as pesticides^{6,7}.

O,O'-Alkylene dithiophosphoric acids, the cyclic analogues of *O,O'*-dialkyl dithiophosphoric acids, have been described⁸ and their metal and organo-metal complexes have been studied extensively in our laboratories⁹⁻¹³. Out of the various possibilities¹⁴ dialkyl and alkylene dithiophosphates generally function as bidentate ligands^{5,8}. An example of unidentate behaviour of dithiophosphate moieties was reported in the case of a transition metal nickel, two coordination positions of which were occupied by a sterically crowded diamine ligand¹⁵. In view of the above, the first reports^{9,16} from our laboratories on monodentate character of dialkyl dithiophosphate with trialkyl as well as triphenyl moieties¹⁷, created considerable interest, as the bidentate nature of these ligands with diorganotin was well established^{9,18,19,20}. The results appear to reflect a lower electrophilicity of trialkyl compared to dialkyltin moieties.

In a recent study, these ligands have been shown to bind phenyl-antimony and -arsenic in a bidentate manner, although there is larger difference between the chelating sulphur atoms in the case of arsenic (0.82 Å) compared to antimony (0.54 Å)²¹. In the present communication, we report the reactions of diphenylantimony(III) chloride with sodium/ammonium salts of *O,O'*-alkylene and diphenyl dithiophosphoric acids which can be represented by the following structures :

Attempts have been made to elucidate the structural features of these derivatives by ir and nmr (^1H , ^{13}C and ^{31}P) spectroscopy as well as molecular weight studied.

Experimental

Infrared spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer and ^1H , ^{13}C and ^{31}P nmr spectra on a Jeol FX90 Q MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal reference (for ^1H and ^{13}C) and TMP (for ^{31}P) as external reference. Molecular weights were determined on Knauer vapour pressure osmometer in chloroform solution.

Stringent precautions were taken to exclude moisture. Diphenylantimony(III) chloride²⁰, alkylene⁸ and diphenyl²¹ dithiophosphoric acids and their sodium/ammonium salts were prepared by the methods described in the literature. Antimony was estimated²² by oxidation method and sulphur as barium sulphate (Messenger's method). Benzene was dried by refluxing over sodium followed by distillation.

Reaction between diphenylantimony(III) chloride and sodium salts of alkylene-dithiophosphate in equimolar ratio: Diphenylantimony(III) chloride dissolved in benzene, was added dropwise to a suspension of sodium dithiophosphate in the same solvent. The mixture was refluxed for ~ 2 h. Sodium chloride formed was removed by filtration. The excess solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the product was finally dried under reduced pressure.

Results and Discussion

Diphenylantimony(III) alkylene (and diphenyl) dithiophosphates have been synthesised in quantitative yields by the reactions of diphenylantimony(III) chloride with sodium/ammonium salts of *O,O'*-alkylene (and diphenyl) dithiophosphoric acids in 1:1 molar ratio in benzene (Table 1). The reactions are quite slow at room temperature but can be pushed to completion in refluxing solvent.

where, M=Na or NH₄, G = -CMe₂CMe₂- (1), -CH₂CMe₂CH₂- (2a), -CH₂CEt₂CH₂- (2b), -CMe₂CH₂CHMe- (3) and OGO = (OPh)₂ (4).

The complexes are colourless or light yellow viscous liquid or semi-solids. The complex 3 which is a colourless viscous liquid when freshly prepared, changed into an orange pasty solid in a fortnight. Other derivatives may be stored unchanged for a long time under reduced pressure. All the complexes are soluble in common organic solvents like benzene, dichloromethane and acetone and also in

coordinating solvents like DMSO and DMF. These compounds appear to be moisture-sensitive.

Ir spectra: Ir spectra (Table 2) have been recorded in the region 4 000–200 cm⁻¹ and tentative assignments have been made on the basis of earlier reports on other metal dithiophosphate derivatives^{22,23-25}. The band due to ν_{SH} present in the region 2 550–2 450 cm⁻¹ in the ir spectra of parent dithiophosphoric acids, is absent in the spectra of the corresponding complexes. Appearance of some new bands of medium intensities in the range 450 ± 10 cm⁻¹ (most probably due to ν_{M-S})^{22,23,27} indicates the formation of these complexes containing metal-sulphur bond. The absorption due to phenyl ring has been observed at 1 010 and 995 cm⁻¹ with sharp to medium intensity bands. The bands at 1 100–1 050 and 870–850 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to ν_{(P)-O-C} and ν_{P-O-(C)} stretching vibrations respectively^{24,26}. The bands at 970–950 cm⁻¹ may be attributed to the ring vibration²⁶. A sharp band present at 695–640 cm⁻¹ is due to ν_{P=S} vibration. The bands at 590–490 and 450–445 cm⁻¹ have been assigned to ν_{P-S} (symmetric

TABLE 1—SYNTHESIS, ANALYTICAL, AND PHYSICAL DATA FOR THE COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Reactants (g)		Product*	Colour/nature	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		Mol. wt. Found/(Calcd.)
	Ph ₂ SbCl	NaS ₂ $\overline{\text{POGO}}$			Sb	S	
1.	1.267	0.974	Ph ₂ SbS ₂ $\overline{\text{POCMe}_2\text{CMe}_2\text{O}}$ (1)	White semi-solid	25.05 (25.01)	13.35 (13.14)	500 (486.75)
2.	0.621	0.433	Ph ₂ SbS ₂ $\overline{\text{POCH}_2\text{CMe}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}}$ (2a)	White yellowish semi-solid	26.13 (25.75)	13.77 (13.53)	498 (472.75)
3.	0.973	0.775	Ph ₂ SbS ₂ $\overline{\text{POCH}_2\text{CEt}_2\text{CH}_2\text{O}}$ (2b)	White semi-solid	24.36 (24.36)	12.93 (12.78)	—
4.	1.034	0.760 ^a	Ph ₂ SbS ₂ $\overline{\text{POCMe}_2\text{CH}_2\text{CHMeO}}$ (3)	Colourless viscous liquid	25.27 (25.01)	13.25 (13.14)	—
5.	0.907	0.886	Ph ₂ SbS ₂ P(OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ (4)	Colourless viscous liquid	21.88 (21.86)	11.66 (11.49)	560 (556.75)

*All product obtained in 90–98% yield. ^aAmmonium salt.

TABLE 2—SOME RELEVANT IR SPECTRAL DATA (cm⁻¹)* FOR THE COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	ν _{(P)-O-C}	ν _{P-O-(C)}	Ring vibrations	ν _{P=S}	ν _{P-S}	ν _{Sb-S}	ν _{Ph-Sb}
1	1 000w	845s	960s	665m	540m	450m	1 015s 995w
2a	1 040s	810s	960m	660m	510m	450m	1 010m 998w
2b	1 040s	830m	945m	650s	510m	445m	1 045m 995w
3	1 045s	835m	940m	640m	500m	448m	1 015m 998w
4	1 050s	890s	970m	695vs	520w	448s	1 010s 998bm

*s=sharp, m=medium, vs=very sharp, w=weak.

and asymmetric) and ν_{Sb-S} respectively. The band due to ν_{P-S} vibrations shows a chemical shift of $15-20\text{ cm}^{-1}$ as compared to their position in the spectra of the corresponding ligands which is suggestive of $S \rightarrow Sb$ coordination, resulting in bidentate nature of bonding in these complexes.

1H nmr spectra: The 1H nmr spectra of these complexes in $CDCl_3$ show characteristic resonance due to glycoxy and phenyl protons (Table 3). A singlet observed at δ 3.10–3.50 in the parent dithio acid and assigned for SH proton⁸, is found to be absent in the spectra of the corresponding diphenylantimony(III) complexes indicating the deprotonation of SH group and formation of Sb–S bond¹¹. A multiplet of phenyl protons is present in the region δ 7.09–7.99. The methylene protons in complexes **2a** and **2b** appear as doublet in the region δ 3.91–4.13 with $J(^1H-^{31}P)$ 17Hz. The OCH protons in complex **3** is present as multiplet at δ 4.64–4.99. In case of complex **4** two multiplets are found at δ 6.77–7.76 for phenoxy and phenyl protons.

TABLE 3— 1H AND ^{31}P NMR SPECTRAL DATA* FOR THE COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	1H chemical shift δ ppm (in $CDCl_3$)	^{31}P chemical shift δ ppm (C_6H_6)
1	1.36 (12H, s, Me), 7.15–7.75 (10H, m, Ph)	105.782
2a	1.01 (6H, s, Me), 3.91–4.10 (4H, d, J 17 Hz, OCH_2), 7.31–7.72 (10H, m, Ph)	90.322
2b	0.763 (6H, t, J 7 Hz Me), 1.27–1.52 (4H, q, CH_2), 3.94–4.13 (4H, d, J 17 Hz, OCH_2), 7.09–7.66 (10H, m, Ph)	91.548
3	1.24–1.71 (11H, m, Me, OH_2), 4.64–4.99 (1H, m, OCH), 7.28–7.79 (10H, m, Ph)	85.826
4	6.77–6.96 (10H, m, OPh), 7.15–7.77 (10H, m, Ph)	90.511

*s=singlet, d=doublet, t=triplet, m=multiplet.

^{13}C nmr spectra: The ^{13}C nmr spectra of the parent dithio acids and their complexes were recorded in chloroform at ambient temperature (Table 4). The spectra of these diphenylantimony(III) complexes show only two bond coupling (with phosphorus) whereas three bond couplings are observed in the

parent dithio acids. In the spectra of these complexes four signals for phenyl carbons have been observed in the region δ 141.66–128.099 ppm for $C_{(i)}$, $C_{(o)}$, $C_{(m)}$ and $C_{(p)}$ respectively. The appearance of single set for the carbons of phenyl group show equivalent nature of phenyl groups. The corrected chemical shift values δ^1 ($\delta^1 = C_{(p)} - C_{(m)}$, where $C_{(p)}$, $C_{(m)}$ are the chemical shift value of *para*- and *meta*-carbons of phenyl groups) are negative for these complexes¹¹. This shows the electron-releasing ability from metal to phenyl ring in these complexes through $p\pi-p\pi$ conjugation. The signals for alkylene carbons were observed at the expected positions.

^{31}P nmr spectra: ^{31}P nmr spectra (proton-decoupled) chemical shift were measured in benzene and summarised in Table 3. The chemical shift of 5-membered parent dithio acids is δ 92.0 ppm while the 6-membered and diphenyl dithio acids show chemical shift of δ 75.0–77.0 and δ 80.0 ppm respectively, thus exhibiting pronounced effect of ring size on ^{31}P chemical shifts⁹. The diphenylantimony(III) complexes show low-field shift of δ 10–15 ppm in ^{31}P signal with respect to parent dithio acids. This is indicative of bidentate⁵ mode of bonding of the ligand moieties in these antimony(III) complexes which is further supported by the ir spectral data.

The above observations based on molecular weight and spectral data are consistent with trigonal bipyramidal geometry for these complexes with two unidentate (phenyl) and one bidentate (dithio-phosphate) moieties in which metal is four-coordinated (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Trigonal bipyramidal structure of diphenylantimony(III) alkylene (and diphenyl) dithiophosphates (where G = $-OCH_2OCH_2-$, $-CH_2OCH_2CH_2-$, $-CH_2C(CH_3)_2CH_2-$, $-OCH_2CH_2CH_2O-$).

TABLE 4— ^{13}C NMR SPECTRAL DATA* OF SOME OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd. no.	Alkylendithiophosphate (in δ ppm)			Diphenylantimony (in δ ppm)				δ^1
	OH_2	OO	>O	$C_{(i)}$	$C_{(o)}$	$C_{(m)}$	$C_{(p)}$	
1	23.892 (s)	90.581 (d, J 2.18 Hz)	—	141.660	136.093	135.166	128.774	–6.392
2a	21.509 (s)	75.757 (d, J 9.48 Hz)	92.291 (s)	141.559	136.141	135.545	128.828	–6.777
4	—	—	—	141.660	136.141	135.491	128.990	–6.501

*s=singlet, d=doublet $C_{(i)}$, $C_{(o)}$, $C_{(m)}$ and $C_{(p)}$ are the chemical shift values of *ipso*, *ortho*, *meta* and *para* carbon atoms of phenyl ring.

Compared to monophenylantimony dithiophosphates in which the ligand has been shown to bind antimony in a bidentate manner with some unidentate tendency as revealed by IR spectroscopy, the bidentate nature of the ligand in the present diphenylantimony (III) derivatives could be explained on the basis of greater electrophilicity of antimony due to higher electron-withdrawing characteristic of the two phenyl groups attached to antimony.

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